

A Combined Experimental and Finite Element Study to Predict
the Failure Mechanisms in SiC Coated Carbon/Carbon Composites
at Room and Elevated Temperatures Under Flexural Loading

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ABSTRACT

Response of quasi-isotropic laminates of SiC coated Carbon/Carbon (C/C) composites have been investigated under flexural loading at various temperatures. Variation of load-deflection behavior with temperatures are studied. Increase in flexural strength and stiffness are observed with the rise in temperature. Extensive analyses through Optical Microscope (OM) and Non-Destructive Evaluation (NDE) have been performed to understand the failure mechanisms. Damage zone is found only within the neighborhood of the loading plane. Isoparametric layered shell elements developed on the basis of the first order shear deformation theory have been used to model the thin laminates of C/C under flexural loading. Large deformation behavior has been considered in the finite element analysis to account for the non-linearities encountered during the actual test. Data generated using finite element analysis are presented to corroborate the experimental findings, and a comparison in respect of displacement and stress-strain behavior are given to check the accuracy of the finite element analysis. Reasonably well correlation between the experimental and finite element results has been established.

Keywords: Flexure, Carbon-Carbon, Finite Element, Failure Mechanism.

1. INTRODUCTION

Research on C/C composites goes back almost two decades, but only after its successful use as thermal protection system in

the wing leading edge and nose cap of the space shuttle, it came into prominence. These earliest forms of C/C are well characterized and in fact were the first to show that C/C composites remain viable structural materials

at temperatures up to 2204°C (4000°F) [1], including the unusual attribute of increasing

strength with temperature up to 2204°C. This unique behavior combined with resistance to catastrophic failure by fiber toughening, good thermal shock resistance and densities below 2 g/cc makes C/C composites the primary candidate for application where operating temperature exceeds 1093°C

(2000°F). Although C/C composites possesses attractive mechanical and physical properties at high temperature, their application as structural materials is currently limited by the susceptibility of carbonaceous materials to oxidation and gasification at elevated temperature. In the absence of a protective coating to inhibit oxidation reactions, carbon fibers can begin to degrade considerably in air

at temperatures as low as 400°C [2]. Much effort is therefore needed to develop techniques for protecting carbon fiber-reinforced materials against oxidation at high temperatures. A potential problem concerning the oxidation protection is the thermal expansion mismatch between the coating and the substrate. Damage initiation in C/C composites during flexural loading has been reported by some researchers [3]. The analysis has been performed at room temperature with uncoated specimens. Two fundamental aspects, namely, the effects of coating and temperature, have not been

studied, which we believe will have considerable influence in the damage mechanisms of C/C. A thorough understanding of the surface chemistry and the oxidation kinetics related to the substrate is therefore required. The matrix in C/C composites is produced either by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) or by impregnation with a carbonaceous liquid pitch or resin followed by carbonization and graphitization. Both methods produce porosity during the carbonization process [4]. In addition, cracks are produced because of the thermal expansion mismatch between the fiber and the carbon matrix. Several infiltration cycles are usually employed, often using successively less viscous infiltrants to obtain materials with desired density. However, the problem of porosity and crack generation at the interface still exists to this day. Moreover, the response of composite materials to any applied load is dependent on the fiber, matrix and the fabrication process, and their performance has been observed to scatter to a large extent [5]. This is because of the fact that flaws are inherent in the composite material from the very fabrication process. It is also well known that a complex damage state is developed in the composite during mechanical loading. To assess this damage either during fabrication or loading, non-destructive evaluation (NDE) is a reliable technique.

Accurate modeling of the nonlinear response of composite materials is a theme that pervades the modern computational solid mechanics and is likely to intensify in the future [6]. The key issue involving both numerical modeling and computational mechanics is the development of numerical technique that can accurately reflect both geometric and material non-linearities, and that can also predict the onset and development of failure. Finite element method is an attractive tool for such rigorous analysis of C/C composites. But the woven structure of the resin impregnated layers and weak interply bonding at lower temperatures sometimes poses questions to the validity of the use of layered shell elements for such studies. However, manufacturing process of C/C composite provides some insight into this problem. The manufacturing steps of C/C [7] indicate that ply orientations are possible in respect of the warp or fill direction of the cloth, and the laminate is expected to exhibit directional property after impregnation and pyrolysis. In fact C/C does demonstrate such behavior and these directional properties are obtainable through characterization. Usually

C/C composite laminates are strong in the plane of the laminate because of the woven fibers, but weak in the thickness direction. If the transverse shear exceeds the interply bonding the laminate can fail in the form of delamination. The prediction and growth of this delamination require an element which can accurately capture the stress field at the ply interfaces [8]. At these ply interfaces transverse strains are discontinuous, and the classical laminate theory ignores it. The improvement over the laminate theories are the higher order shear deformation theories where displacements are expressed with higher order expansions through the laminate thickness. Layered shell element considering these higher order theories is still in the development stage [9].

In this paper, a combined experimental - analytical investigation on the flexural response of SiC coated C/C composites (ACC-4) is presented at room and elevated temperatures. The load-deflection behavior at various temperatures is examined and the variation in flexural strength and stiffness with temperatures has been investigated. Crack initiation and propagation at room temperature are studied thoroughly under incremental loading using Optical Microscopy (OM) and Non-Destructive Evaluation (NDE) to predict the failure mechanisms. On the other hand, 8 noded isoparametric layered shell element developed on the basis of the first order shear deformation theory is used to study the non-linear response of symmetric 8-ply C/C composite under flexural loading. Results of extensive finite element analysis are presented to augment the experimental investigation of the failure mechanisms of Carbon-Carbon composites as well as to develop a useful analytical tool for the failure prediction of this material.

2. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

2.1 Material and Specimen Preparation

The fabrication of the material began with satin woven cloth of 3k T-300 yarns which was converted into graphite and impregnated with a phenolic resin. This impregnated cloth was laid up in [+45, 90, -45, 0]_s sequence, as shown in Fig. 1, to form the laminate, and was cured in an autoclave. After curing, the laminate was pyrolyzed at high temperature to convert the resin to carbon. To improve the structure of the porous matrix the laminate was then carbon impregnated. The impregnation and pyrolysis

were repeated four times to achieve the desired density of about 1.6 gm/cc. A fiber volume fraction of 64% was maintained in the final uncoated specimens. The specimens were then pack cemented with SiC coating which were embedded with glass sealants. The coating thickness was maintained between 100 and 120 micron. All flexure tests were conducted using three point beam. The loading and the specimen dimensions are shown in Fig. 2(a).

2.2. Flexure Test

The flexural strength and stiffness were determined at room, 649°C (1200°F) and 1371°C (2500°F) temperature in air by using the 3-point bend test. All the flexural tests were carried out according to ASTM standard D-790. An Instron 8502 test machine with series-IX data acquisition system was used. For high temperature tests, the 3-point bend fixture was fabricated from cast SiC and the push rods were made of alumina. The outer and inner span of the specimen are shown in Fig. 2(a). The cross head speed for all tests was 0.254 mm/min (0.01 inch/min). The speed was kept low to minimize any catastrophic failure and to allow the maximum time possible for observation of damage and its progression. The equations used for evaluating the flexural strength and stiffness were the typical 3-point beam equations derived from the Euler-Bernoulli beam theory. At R.T., the load was applied incrementally in difference of 44.48 N, starting from 88.96 N. At the end of each load step, the specimen was taken out to study the crack initiation and propagation using OM and at the same time, C-Scans were taken to understand the progressive failure mechanisms within the material. The maximum load obtained during incremental tests agreed with its one step flexural tests. Therefore, the results were not affected by the removal and reinsertion of the specimens during incremental loading. During the high temperature tests, the furnace was heated gradually at a rate of 10°C/min. After reaching the test temperature, the isothermal condition was maintained for about half an hour during which the test was conducted and then the furnace was cooled down, again at 10°C/min.

2.3. Non-Destructive Evaluation

The non-destructive evaluation of the

fractured as well as untested specimens were performed in a Test Tech Ultrasonic Scanning machine equipped with DAS-100 data acquisition system. Sound in the 10 MHz frequency range was produced by pulsing a lithium sulphite transducer which also functioned as the receiver element. The resulting waveform was digitized to 8 bits and processed by the microcomputer. The microcomputer also controlled the movement of the x-y scanner. The imaging of the data obtained through the ultrasonic scanning for various specimens were stored and eventually plotted.

3. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

3.1. Model Development

A non-linear Finite Element Analysis (FEA) using ANSYS was conducted in order to predict damage initiation analytically in the tested specimens. Flexural test coupons of satin woven quasi-isotropic laminates of C/C coated with SiC are modeled with 8-noded isoparametric layered shell elements. The formulation of the shell element used in the investigation was based on the Mindlin's [10] theory that the mid-surface normal after deformation would remain straight but not necessarily normal to the mid-surface. This allowed transverse shear deformation to take into account. However, this transverse shear deformation has been assumed to remain constant through the thickness of the laminate limiting the current FEA to what is widely known as first order shear deformation theory. The discretized model and the boundary conditions for the flexural tests are shown in Fig. 2(b). Three different temperatures, R.T. (23°C/75°F), 649°C (1200°F) and 1371°C (2500°F) similar to the experimental tests were considered in the finite element analysis to verify the thermal expansion effect at elevated temperatures. Large deflection effect on the geometry was considered to approximate the finite element model to the closest proximity of the experimental tests. Multiple load steps and the updating of the stiffness matrix at each load step were considered to account for the geometric non-linearity. Maximum stress failure theory was applied to evaluate the failure criteria numbers.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Typical stress-strain behavior of

flexural test at R.T., 649°C (1200°F) and 1371°C (2500°F) temperatures are shown in Fig. 3. It can be observed that both strength and stiffness increase with temperatures. The computed displacement using FEA model is compared with the load-displacement curve at R.T. in Fig. 4(a). These two curves are in good agreement with each other. The comparison at 1371°C is shown in Figs. 4(b). The increase in strength and stiffness with the increase in temperatures are believed to be due to the stronger fiber/matrix interfacial bonding at elevated temperatures. Finite element analysis results shown in Fig. 5 indicates that 45° plies (layer2 and layer9) are experiencing the highest stress in the laminate throughout the incremental loading. However, stress on coating is about 138 MPa (20 ksi) which is much higher than on 45° plies. Since with the input of modulus of elasticity for coating and laminate remain same in the FEA under flexural loading, the reason for higher stress in coating is that the coating has the lower thickness than other plies of the laminate. Therefore, we can predict that large magnitude of σ_x at the coating will most likely lead to coating cracks which will eventually put excessive reliance on the glass sealant at elevated temperatures. Figures. 6(a)–6(f), taken from the side as well as from the bottom layer (tensile side) of the specimen, show the crack propagation in the specimen with the increase in load at room temperature. Visual observations indicate that all failures are on the tensile side, and show no damage on the compression side. The crack starts initiating only after the application of 180 N, shown in Figs. 6(a) & 6(b). A small crack in the transverse direction can be seen as the load is increased to 222 N. In the next step, with the increase in load to 227 N as shown in Figs. 6(c) and 6(d), the crack develops vertically through the substrate layers and then propagates horizontally along the fiber bundle, leading to the final failure of the specimen. Crack propagation after attaining the maximum load is shown in Figs. 6(e) and 6(f). This crack initiation and propagation takes place at the very end of the ultimate flexural load. This becomes more clear from the NDE Figs. 7(a)–7(e), which are taken at the end of each load step described previously. The more is the interface loss, the more is the damage in the laminate. First two figures, 7(a) & 7(b), are the ultrasonic C-Scans of untested specimen, and after 180 N load, respectively. They indicate no significant damage. Minor damage in the middle of the specimen is observed in Fig. 7(c), at 222 N load is achieved. Severe damage, as indicated by black portion in Fig. 7(d) is observed only after its ultimate load. Once initiated the damage continues to propagate in the laminate as shown in the Fig. 7(e), even with the load gradually decreasing. It is interesting to note that the areas near the support ends of the laminate show no indication of damage during flexure tests. This is contrary to what has been reported by the reference [6]. It is believed that higher span-to-depth ratio ($L/d = 33.75$) used in the current research is the reason for localizing the damage only near the loading plane.

Variation of stress through the thickness of the laminate at three temperatures are shown in Fig. 8. Insignificant change of stress values with temperatures have been observed except at the coatings. It is found that at room temperature the stress distribution is nonlinear but almost symmetric along the thickness of the specimen, and the maximum stress on the outer layers are close to the experimental values. But at high temperatures stress distribution becomes also nonlinear and non-symmetric which is believed to be due to the thermal expansion. The FEA results at elevated temperatures overestimates the stress values in the outer layers, but the substrate stresses are lower than the experimental values. Interlaminar shear stress distributions along the thickness of the specimen, both at room temperature and high temperatures are shown in Fig. 9. The distribution is parabolic and maximum interlaminar shear stress occurs between layer-5 and layer-6 which correlates with the prediction by Euler-Bernoulli beam theory. However, the magnitude of interlaminar shear stress is well below the corresponding composite strength indicating that delamination is most unlikely to occur even at high temperatures. The failure of the specimen therefore remains to be caused either by fiber breakage or matrix cracking in the neighborhood of the maximum membrane stress. The stress distribution at each layer of the laminate was also investigated through finite element analysis. Figures 10(a) and 10(b) show the stress (σ_x and σ_y) contour of the substrate layer (45° ply), which indicate that the maximum value of all membrane stress takes place at the neighborhood of the

applied load. The plot obtained through the ultrasonic C-Scans of fractured specimen, shown in Fig. 7(e), confirms the FEA prediction. At elevated temperatures, stress contours obtained from FEA are same except that the magnitude of the stress values are higher. Good correlation in respect of maximum deflection between the experimental and FEA is observed in Fig. 11. Since deflection is the most reliable data from the experiment, it suggests that the layered shell element with first order shear deformation assumption can be used for thin C/C structures.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The combined experimental-analytical investigations show good correlation regarding the prediction of the failure mechanisms in SiC coated C/C composites. The flexural strength and stiffness have been observed to increase with temperature. The failure was always found on the tensile side. Stronger interfacial bonding is believed to be responsible for such behavior at elevated temperatures. Crack initiation takes place only on the outer surface (coating-tensile side), then propagates rapidly at the very end of its ultimate flexural load. The damage zone is found in the neighborhood of the loading plane. It is successfully shown that thin laminates of coated Carbon-Carbon composites can be modeled using layered shell element developed on the basis of the first order shear deformation theory. Reasonably well correlation between the experimental results and the finite element analysis in respect of global maximum displacement has been observed. Non-linear distributions of interlaminar shear stress (ILSUM) and flexural stress (σ_x) have been found through the laminate thickness. In-plane distributions of flexural stresses (σ_x & σ_y) have shown that the maximum value of stresses occur near the middle of the specimens suggesting that in the ideal situation in absence of matrix flaws, crack will initiate at the loading plane, which clearly supports the experimental observation.

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Fig. 1 (a) Laid Up Sequence of Laminate
(b) Satin Woven Structure of a ply

Fig. 2(a): Problem Sketch

Fig. 2(b): Finite Element Model

Fig. 3: Typical Stress-Strain Behavior of C/C Composite Under Flexural Loading (Expt.)

Fig. 4(a): Comparison between Expt. and FEA with Load-Displacement Curve at RT

Fig. 4(b): Comparison between Expt. and FEA with Load-Displacement Curve at 1371°C

Fig. 5 Variations of Stress (σ_x) at Layer 2-5 With Load Increments (Flexural Test)

Fig 6(a) Bottom View of the Flexural Specimen at Initial Stage of Loading (180N)

Fig 6(e) Crack Propagation after Attaining the Maximum Load

Fig 6(b) Corresponding Side View

Fig 6(f) Corresponding Side View

Fig 6(c): Crack Initiation at the Bottom at the End of Loading (227N)

Fig 6(d) Corresponding Side View

RANGE (%)		COLOR
FROM	TO	
Interface down		
100.00	80.00	
80.00	60.00	
60.00	40.00	
40.00	20.00	
20.00	0.00	

Fig 7(a) Ultrasonic C-Scan before the test

Fig 7(b) Ultrasonic C-Scan after 180N Load

Fig 7(c): Ultrasonic C-Scan after 222N Load

Fig 7(d) Ultrasonic C-Scan after 227N Load

Fig 7(e): Ultrasonic C-Scan after failure

Fig 10(a)

Stress (S_x) distribution at Layer 2 (Flexural Test)

Fig. 8 Variations of Stress (σ_x) Along Thickness of the Laminate Under Flexural Test

Fig 10(b)

Stress (S_y) distribution at Layer 2 (Flexural Test)

Fig. 9: Interlaminar Shear Stress Distribution Through Thickness of the Laminate Under Flexural Loading

Fig. 11: Comparison with Respect to Maximum Deflection between the Expt. and FEA